

Allometric relationships used in the CARAT and ACORN tools to assess evolution of tree biomass and tree carbon storage over time for 19 tree species in temperate agroforestry

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Introduction

Agroforestry is receiving increasing attention in temperate agricultural systems as a promising agroecological practice. It can contribute to climate change mitigation and adaptation, as well as greater diversity and resilience on the farm. Additionally, agroforestry provides opportunities to compensate for lower crop yields through the production of wood, fruit, or nuts.

Several calculation tools (see also [DigitAF tool catalogue](#)) have been developed to quantitatively assess ecosystem services and/or productivity within agroforestry systems, among others the CARAT and ACORN tools, which are part of the "[Agroforestry Planner Flanders](#)".

ACORN supports the design of agroforestry systems by combining simulations of crop yields, crop quality, and wood production with an economic evaluation. The tool focuses on alley-cropping systems and simulates yields over a ten-year period following the establishment of the alley-cropping system.

CARAT (CARbon Agroforestry Tool) was developed to quantify the carbon sequestration in agroforestry systems. It currently focuses on high stem trees in alley cropping or silvopastoral systems.

Both tools require **calculation of the (temporal evolution of) tree biomass**, for which we use allometric relationships based on the diameter at breast height (DBH). This is done in two steps: (1) predicting the development of DBH as a function of time, and (2) calculating biomass based on the estimated DBH using allometric relations and species-specific wood density values.

Next, also the (temporal evolution of) **carbon storage in tree biomass** can ultimately be determined by multiplying the total above-ground biomass by a factor of 47% (a typical value used for trees in temperate forests; IPCC 2006).

In this brief overview, we share the allometric relationships which are currently (April 2026) used for 19 tree species in temperate regions. We also add the exemplary calculation for an individual Poplar and Walnut tree, for the first twenty years after planting. Note that we currently also continue to collect empirical data in real-farm agroforestry context, so as to further calibrate these relationships in the near future.

Diameter at Breast Height

For 19 tree species, DBH is modelled as a function of time. The relationship between DBH and age is species-specific and was estimated based on several sources: Van Den Berge et al. (2021) for hedgerow trees in Flanders; Lukaszkiwicz & Kosmala (2008) for urban trees in Poland; Monteiro et al. (2017) for urban trees in Great Britain; and Carton (2022) and Pardon (2018) for poplar in Flanders (see Table 1).

From each of these studies, the raw data (DBH as a function of age) were extracted. A logistic function (Eq. 1) was subsequently fitted to each individual dataset. This type of relationship is commonly used in ecology to approximate tree growth dynamics.

$$DBH = \frac{a}{e^{b-ct}} \quad \text{[Equation 1]}$$

where a , b , and c are species-specific model parameters and t represents the tree age (in years). The model parameters were estimated for each tree species and study by minimizing the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE). For tree species for which no relationship was available in the literature, growth rates were approximated by comparison with other species for which growth relationships were available. When two or more growth functions were available for a given species, the curve that best reflected growth under open-grown conditions (e.g., urban trees) was selected (see Table 1).

For each tree on the plot and at each time step, the model calculates DBH based on the corresponding equations. These DBH values are subsequently used as input for the biomass model.

Table 1: Diameter at Breast Height (DBH) [cm] as a function of age (t) [years] for the different agroforestry tree species.

Tree species	Growth rate	Equation	Source
<i>Acer pseudoplatanus</i>	Fast	= 61/(1+exp(2-0.059*t))	Monteiro et al. (2017)
<i>Alnus glutinosa</i>	Fast	= 728/(1+exp(4.62-0.035*t))	Van De Berge et al. (2021)
<i>Aesculus hippocastanum</i>	Medium	= 52.8/(1+exp(2.02-0.069*t))	Lukaszkiwicz & Kosmala (2008)
<i>Corylus avellana</i>	Medium	= 89.9/(1+exp(2.28-0.04*t))	Lukaszkiwicz & Kosmala (2008)
<i>Fraxinus excelsior</i>	Fast	= 68.7/(1+exp(2.7-0.072*t))	Lukaszkiwicz & Kosmala (2008)
<i>Juglans regia</i>	Medium	= 89.9/(1+exp(2.28-0.04*t))	Lukaszkiwicz & Kosmala (2008)
<i>Malus domestica</i>	Medium	= 89.9/(1+exp(2.28-0.04*t))	Lukaszkiwicz & Kosmala (2008)
<i>Populus x canadensis</i>	Very fast	= 65.6/(1+exp(2.12-0.187*t))	Carton et al. (2022)
<i>Prunus avium</i>	Fast	= 89.9/(1+exp(2.28-0.04*t))	Lukaszkiwicz & Kosmala (2008)
<i>Pyrus communis</i>	Medium	= 89.9/(1+exp(2.28-0.04*t))	Lukaszkiwicz & Kosmala (2008)
<i>Quercus petraea</i>	Slow	= 60.2/(1+exp(2-0.061*t))	Van De Berge et al. (2021)
<i>Quercus robur</i>	Slow	= 60.2/(1+exp(2-0.061*t))	Van De Berge et al. (2021)
<i>Robinia pseudoacacia</i>	Fast	= 1452.5/(1+exp(5.66-0.041*t))	Van De Berge et al. (2021)
<i>Salix</i> sp.	Fast	= 1452.5/(1+exp(5.66-0.041*t))	Van De Berge et al. (2021)
<i>Sorbus aucuparia</i>	Medium	= 89.9/(1+exp(2.28-0.04*t))	Lukaszkiwicz & Kosmala (2008)
<i>Sorbus torminalis</i>	Medium	= 89.9/(1+exp(2.28-0.04*t))	Lukaszkiwicz & Kosmala (2008)
<i>Tilia cordata</i>	Medium	= 89.9/(1+exp(2.28-0.04*t))	Lukaszkiwicz & Kosmala (2008)
<i>Tilia platyphyllos</i>	Medium	= 89.9/(1+exp(2.28-0.04*t))	Lukaszkiwicz & Kosmala (2008)
<i>Ulmus</i> sp.	Fast	= 61/(1+exp(2-0.059*t))	Monteiro et al. (2017)

Biomass

To quantify the aboveground woody biomass of the different trees on the plot, allometric relationships based on DBH were used. These relationships were derived for each tree species from literature: Shafer et al. (2019) provided biomass equations for trees in food forests, McPherson et al. (2016) provided volume equations for urban trees in the USA, and Hjelm & Johansson (2012) provided volume equations for poplars in Sweden. When no allometric relationship was available, we used data from species with comparable growth rates. (see Table 2). When only an allometric relationship for aboveground volume was available, wood density was obtained from the Global Wood Density Database (Zanne et al., 2009). Multiplying wood density by volume then allows calculation of total aboveground biomass.

Table 2: Allometric relationships for aboveground biomass [kg] based on diameter at breast height (DBH) [cm] for the 19 tree species. The equations were derived from the literature for the corresponding tree species in an urban forest or food forest context.

Tree species	Equation	Source
<i>Acer pseudoplatanus</i>	$= (520/1000) * (0.0019421 * DBH^{1.785})$	McPherson et al. (2016)
<i>Alnus glutinosa</i>	$= 0.00079 * DBH^{2.28546}$	Shafer et al. (2019)
<i>Aesculus hippocastanum</i>	$= (580/1000) * (0.0002431 * DBH^{2.415})$	McPherson et al. (2016)
<i>Corylus avellana</i>	$= \exp(-2.2118 + 2.4133 * \ln(DBH))$	Shafer et al. (2019)
<i>Fraxinus excelsior</i>	$= (530/1000) * (0.0005885 * DBH^{2.206})$	McPherson et al. (2016)
<i>Juglans regia</i>	$= \exp(-2.2118 + 2.4133 * \ln(DBH))$	Shafer et al. (2019)
<i>Malus domestica</i>	$= \exp(-2.2118 + 2.4133 * \ln(DBH))$	Shafer et al. (2019)
<i>Populus × canadensis</i>	$= (370/1000) * (\exp(0.3285 * \ln(dbh)^{2.2502}))$	Hjelm & Johansson (2012)
<i>Prunus avium</i>	$= \exp(-2.2118 + 2.4133 * \ln(DBH))$	Shafer et al. (2019)
<i>Pyrus communis</i>	$= \exp(-2.2118 + 2.4133 * \ln(DBH))$	Shafer et al. (2019)
<i>Quercus petraea</i>	$= (580/1000) * (0.0002431 * DBH^{2.415})$	McPherson et al. (2016)
<i>Quercus robur</i>	$= (580/1000) * (0.0002431 * DBH^{2.415})$	McPherson et al. (2016)
<i>Robinia pseudoacacia</i>	$= 4.13741 * DBH^{2.17752}$	McPherson et al. (2016)
<i>Salix sp.</i>	$= 0.454 * 10^{(0.8856 + 2.0552 * \log(2.54 * DBH))}$	Shafer et al. (2019)
<i>Sorbus aucuparia</i>	$= \exp(-2.2118 + 2.4133 * \ln(DBH))$	Shafer et al. (2019)
<i>Sorbus torminalis</i>	$= \exp(-2.2118 + 2.4133 * \ln(DBH))$	Shafer et al. (2019)
<i>Tilia cordata</i>	$= \exp(-2.6788 + 2.4542 * \ln(DBH))$	Shafer et al. (2019)
<i>Tilia platyphyllos</i>	$= \exp(-2.6788 + 2.4542 * \ln(DBH))$	Shafer et al. (2019)
<i>Ulmus sp.</i>	$= (460/1000) * (0.0018 * DBH^{1.869})$	McPherson et al. (2016)

Indicative examples of calculation for Poplar and Walnut*

POPLAR

Age	DBH (cm)	AGB (kg)	Carbon stored in AGB (kg)
1	8,29	2,18	1,02
2	9,75	3,00	1,41
3	11,40	4,21	1,98
4	13,27	6,00	2,82
5	15,36	8,65	4,07
6	17,67	12,59	5,92
7	20,18	18,39	8,64
8	22,89	26,82	12,60
9	25,75	38,86	18,26
10	28,72	55,71	26,18
11	31,77	78,67	36,97
12	34,83	109,03	51,25
13	37,86	147,90	69,51
14	40,80	195,94	92,09
15	43,61	253,22	119,01
16	46,26	319,11	149,98
17	48,71	392,26	184,36
18	50,95	470,79	221,27
19	52,96	552,45	259,65
20	54,76	634,92	298,41

DBH = Diameter at Breast Height

AGB = Aboveground Biomass

WALNUT

Age	DBH (cm)	AGB (kg)	Carbon stored in AGB (kg)
1	8,65	19,98	9,39
2	8,97	21,80	10,25
3	9,30	23,78	11,18
4	9,63	25,92	12,18
5	9,98	28,25	13,28
6	10,34	30,78	14,47
7	10,72	33,51	15,75
8	11,10	36,48	17,15
9	11,49	39,69	18,66
10	11,90	43,17	20,29
11	12,32	46,93	22,06
12	12,75	51,00	23,97
13	13,20	55,39	26,03
14	13,65	60,13	28,26
15	14,12	65,24	30,66
16	14,61	70,76	33,26
17	15,10	76,69	36,05
18	15,61	83,09	39,05
19	16,13	89,96	42,28
20	16,67	97,35	45,75

DBH = Diameter at Breast Height

AGB = Aboveground Biomass

**The calculations presented in this table are not generally valid. Tree growth is always dependent on plot specific (micro)climate, soil conditions and other context specific aspects such as plant quality, management etc. The results for walnut seem to be rather on the low side.*

Therefore, they represent possible trends and order-of-magnitude results, but do not constitute exact predictions. They are intended to support the exploration, design, planning, and comparison of scenarios.

Based upon :

- [CARAT manual](#) (Dutch)
- [ACORN manual](#) (English)
- Vanneste et al. 2025. CARAT : an innovative tool for quantifying carbon sequestration in agroforestry systems. Agroforestry Systems 99. DOI: [10.1007/s10457-025-01162-3](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10457-025-01162-3)

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Disclaimer

The relationships presented in this document need further validation in agroforestry specific context. Tree growth is always dependent on plot specific (micro)climate, soil conditions and other context specific aspects such as plant quality, management etc.

Therefore, they represent possible trends, relative differences, and order-of-magnitude effects, but do not constitute exact predictions. They are intended to support the exploration, design, planning, and comparison of scenarios.

ILVO and the partners of the Agroforestry Flanders Consortium cannot be held liable for decisions or consequences resulting from the use of this tool. For feedback, questions, or comments, you can always contact us via info@agroforestryvlaanderen.be.